

ISic1623

I.Sicily inscription 1623

Language

Oscan

Type

dedication (?)

Material

limestone (conchiferous)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Messina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 171043

Bibliography

Vetter, E. 1953. Handbuch der italischen Dialekte. Heidelberg. At no.197a

Orsi, P. 1916. Messana. La necropoli romana di S. Placido e di altre scoperte avvenute nel 1910-1915. *Monumenti Antichi*. 24: 121-218. At 195 fig.46

Crawford, M.H. 2011. Imagines Italicae. A Corpus of Italic Inscriptions. *Bulletin of the Institute of Classical Studies Supplement 111*. London. At Messana 7

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